

CULTURAL ASPECTS OF KAZAKH PLACE NAMES IN CHINESE TERRITORY

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Abstract: *Place names do not merely refer to geographical objects of a specific region, but also serve as an important indicator of the culture, history, worldview, and lifestyle of a people. Each nation has its own distinctive characteristics in naming places, which reflect their national identity and culture. For the Kazakh people, the cultural aspects of place names hold special significance as well.*

The Kazakh population in China, who have long adhered to a nomadic lifestyle, have preserved their national and cultural characteristics in place names. For them, these names represent a clear reflection of their ancestors' way of life, history, and relationship with nature. The Kazakhs living in China's Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region have expressed their culture and language through place names.

This article explores the cultural and linguistic aspects of Kazakh place names in Chinese territory. Specifically, it aims to examine how these names reflect the culture, history, and lifestyle of the Kazakh people, and what role they currently play. Additionally, the study seeks to showcase the national consciousness and cultural uniqueness through the investigation of the toponymic system in the regions inhabited by Kazakhs in China.

Keywords: *place names, toponyms, culture, folklore, mythology, history,*

The study of Kazakh toponyms in China is of great importance today, as it is closely related to the problems of preserving and studying the cultural and historical heritage of the Kazakh people. The kazakh toponyms in China are an important detail of national identity and historical memory. The study of this topic is relevant for the preservation of national culture and its transmission to the next generations in the context of modern globalization. In addition, this study helps to understand the

cultural and linguistic conditions in the regions where the Kazakh diaspora lives in China.

The Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region is a unique region in geographical and cultural terms. Toponyms in Xinjiang are witnesses of many historical events. The names of the region varied over the centuries, with each political period leaving its mark, with some names newly given or changed in Chinese. For example, the name Xinjiang itself "新疆" ("Xinjiang") means "New Frontier" and was introduced during the Qing dynasty in the eighteenth century.

Xinjiang is very rich in natural resources and minerals, which is why it has long been called a "treasure land". For the same reason, many places are named after local products and minerals, which indicates local features. In the 50s of the 20th century, the names of land-water, mountains, rivers were used as an important source in the search for minerals. There are many such examples. For example, the name Altai Mountain (阿尔泰山) in Mongolian means "golden mountain", because gold is mined here in large quantities. According to historical data, thousands of people came to this region for gold mining. Altai district also comes from this name, but the word "Altai" also means "golden" in the Kazakh language. In addition, Fuyun (富蕴县) district in the Altai territory is also so named because there are abundant fossils (gold, precious stones, crystals, copper, iron, nickel, beryllium, niobium, lithium, etc. more than 70) underground, the name is borrowed from Chinese [DONG Yinqi 2008: 8].

The first major oil field explored after the founding of the people's Republic of China, the city of Karamay (克拉玛依), was founded in 1958, so named because of the abundance of oil. The origin of the name of the city is due to mount Karamay, located in the Northeast, which in the Kazakh language means "Karamai". Also, the names of places such as Saltykol and Tuztobe were given due to the fact that there are abundant salt reserves in these places. Since the climate of Xinjiang is dry, many areas are semi-desert, there are many such salty places, and most of them are associated with the word "salt".

Moyu district (墨玉县) in the Khotan region in Southern Xinjiang comes from the name of the Karakash (喀拉喀什河) River. "Karakash" means "black jade" in Uyghur. Since there is a lot of black jade in this region, the name reflects the local identity and means that it is rich in minerals.

There are many Kazakh land and water names in the regions with a large population of Kazakh people in Nylky, Zhana, Tekes, Shapshal and Kulzha districts. For example, in the Nylky district there are such names as: Uzun (乌赞) village;

karatobe (喀拉托别) village; Karasu (喀拉苏) Village; copper ("there is a copper ore") village; Kach (means "the most beautiful river") [NIU Ruji 1995: 11].

In Shapshal district, there are such place names as: Kayyndybulak River (喀因德布拉); Muzart river (木扎尔特); Budasai (布达萨依); Kostobe village (阔斯托别); Aktas village (阿克塔斯).

In the Zhana district there are such toponyms as: Tayazsu (塔亚苏) village; Kensu (坎苏) village; Asauz (阿萨阿吾孜) village.

In the Tekes area: Teryskeytau (铁尔斯开依套), Pyshaksalma (皮夹克萨勒玛) river; Kumtubek (库木托别克); Karatogay (喀拉托海) village; Sholakterek (乔拉克铁热克) village; Tykzhol village (特克卓勒) village names.

In Kulzha district there is the village of Tykaryk (提克阿热克).

The middle part of the Tian Shan Mountains is called the Erenkabyrga (依连哈比噶尔: similar to a human wall, steep and rocky) mountain. There are also such names as the peak of Kabanbai (batyr of the Kazakh people) and the village of Agarsyn (阿哈尔森).

It is possible to encounter several cultural aspects of Kazakh land and water names on the territory of China:

Historical features

The history of life of Kazakhs in China covers a long time. They migrated for centuries and practiced nomadism in the vast steppes. This traditional way of life directly influenced the formation of land and water names. The Kazakhs named each place in their own way, using the same names they described the specifics of the land and its place in human life. For example, such names as "Karatau", "Bulanti", "Tarbagatay" reflect the geographical landscape and history of the Earth.

Mythology and folklore

Part of the Kazakh names of places is inextricably linked with folk mythology. Many names are associated with fairy-tale characters, heroes or legends. For example, the name "Dragon's Mane" may have been based on a local legend, which mentions the enormous power of the Dragon and its power there. Such names characterize the spiritual world, worldview and history of the people. In addition, many names include the names of natural phenomena and mythological characters, which indicates the connection of the Kazakhs with nature and its reverence.

Relationship with nature

Since the nomadic way of life depends on Nature, place and water names are rich in natural features. For example, the names "Koksai" or "Shubarkol" mean vegetation and water resources of the same region. The word "Kok" in the Kazakh

language means the purity of the sky, nature, freedom and breadth, and "Sai " means a valley, a ravine of a river. Through these names, the Kazakhs show that they lived in harmony with nature. The nomadic way of life formed a special relationship of the kazakhs with nature. This connection is clearly reflected in the names of places and waters. Many names are associated with the land's landscape, vegetation, or water resources. For example, such names as "Ural "(river),"Saryarka" (vast steppe) or "Karasu" (river or stream) emphasize the distinctive features of nature and reflect the features of the place [Толкын, Қалибекулы 2022: 5]. Kazakhs perceived nature not only as a source of life, but also as an integral part of cultural and spiritual values.

Most of Xinjiang consists of mountainous, semi-desert and steppe territories, so toponyms are often based on the natural landscape. Many names are associated with mountains, rivers, deserts and other natural objects. For example:

- Tian Shan (大山) — means "Heavenly mountains" in Chinese. This chain of mountains is one of the main geographical features of Xinjiang.

- Tarym- lowland or tarym River, a name associated with the natural resources and peculiarities of the climate of the region.

Economic and economic activities

Most of the Kazakh land and water names are associated with animal husbandry. For example, the name "Zhailau" refers to the vast steppes used as summer recreation and cattle grazing. Thus, land and water names are also a reflection of the main part of the Kazakh way of life – Animal Husbandry. For Kazakhs engaged in nomadic animal husbandry, such names as zhailau, kystau, kokteu and kuzeu mean not only geographical features, but also important aspects of the way of life of the people. If "zhailau" is a summer pasture,"Kystau" is a place for keeping livestock in winter, then these names reflect the economic experience of the Kazakhs, interconnected with nature.

Preservation of culture and language

The Kazakhs of China have preserved their language, culture, traditions and Customs in the names of places. These names reflect the national identity and cultural characteristics of the Kazakhs. The abundance of place and water names in Xinjiang in the Kazakh language is one of the proofs of the ethnic and cultural integrity of the Kazakhs in that region.

Xinjiang is home to several ethnic groups, the largest of which are uyghurs, kazakhs, chinese (han), kyrgyz, dungans and others. This diversity is reflected in toponyms, since geographical names are formed in different languages — uyghur, kazakh, chinese, mongolian, tajik, etc. For example, Kashgar (喀什) is a name of ; Uyghur origin, the name "Kashi" means "fortress", "mound" [Koibakova 2024: 9].

Influence of religion and culture

The influence of Islam, Buddhism and local religious beliefs on names in Chinese territory, including Xinjiang, was also significant. Many cities and place names are named in honor of Islamic culture, holy places, or religious figures. For example, Khotan (和田) is a city that was the center of Buddhist and later Islamic culture. This name was known in ancient times as an important religious and commercial center.

Influence of Turkic and Persian languages

For a long time, Xinjiang was an important part of the Great Silk Road, which contributed to the influence of Turkic and Persian languages on its names. The abundance of Persian and Turkic names indicates cultural exchanges in the history of this region. For example, the name Yarkent (Shakiryu) is known as a historical shopping center. The meaning of the name yarkent means "foreign region" and comes from the Turkic languages.

The importance of Kazakh toponyms

In the regions of Xinjiang, where Kazakhs are most concentrated, Kazakh toponyms are common. They are often names related to natural features, animal husbandry, or historical events. The preservation of Kazakh toponyms reflects the richness of the ethnic culture of the region [Kalibekuly 2023: 6]. For example, the name of the Ili River has been preserved in Kazakh and other Turkic languages. This name indicates that the river is important for the region.

Conclusion

Kazakh land and water names in China are not only geographical names, but also an important cultural phenomenon that reflects the culture, history, mythology and connection of the people with nature. Through these names, kazakhs pass on their spiritual and material wealth to the next generation. The study of the names of places reveals one of the aspects of the cultural and ethnic identity of Kazakhs in China, and allows us to understand more deeply their interaction with nature and society.

Place and water names determine the linguistic and ethnolinguistic features of the Kazakh people. Each name reflects the linguistic characteristics of the population, vocabulary and linguistic culture. Through toponyms, special concepts, lexical and grammatical structures characteristic of the Kazakh language are preserved. Thus, place and water names are an important tool for maintaining the vitality of the language and transmitting it to future generations.

Cultural aspects of place and water names are an important cultural phenomenon that reflects the history, spiritual world, economic life and linguistic features of the people. For the Kazakh people, place and water names are a value that reflects the

national identity, worldview and relationship with nature. Through these names, cultural continuity between generations is preserved, and the historical and spiritual heritage of the people is transmitted from generation to generation.

Turkic toponyms on the territory of China, including Kazakh toponyms, are important as a reflection of ethnic, linguistic and historical features. The names of this region reflect its rich culture, multinational structure and historical events. The study of toponyms in Xinjiang is not limited only to the recognition of geographical objects, but allows a deeper understanding of the history and culture of the region.

The topic of Kazakh land and water names in China has not yet been sufficiently studied. Although there are some ethnographic and historical studies, there are not enough full-fledged and comprehensive works on the toponyms of this region. Despite the fact that research in this area has been conducted among Kazakh and Chinese scientists, this topic still requires a deep and comprehensive study.

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